

Pilot tests at SINTEF: Reducing carbon footprint in manganese ferroalloy production: HAIMan project explores hydrogen as a reductant

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Manganese is a crucial alloying element for steels. However, the production of manganese ferroalloys generates significant CO₂ emissions due to the use of fossil carbon as a reductant. There is potential to substitute carbon with hydrogen. Although complete reduction of manganese oxides to manganese metal is theoretically impossible, the EU co-funded HAIMan project is testing hydrogen as a reductant to partially reduce manganese ores. As part of this project, a pilot-scale experiment involving the hydrogen reduction of approximately 300 kg of manganese ore has been conducted. In the upcoming pilot trials, around 500 kg of manganese ore will be used. Overall, the project plans to conduct four pilot tests, each utilizing 500 kg of manganese ore in subsequent trials.

Step-by-Step process

1st step

This manganese ore comes from the N'chwaning mine in South Africa. It serves as the primary material used for testing and is loaded into the furnace. Each trial involves 500 kg, with a total of 4 trials conducted.

01

02

2nd step

This is the rotary furnace from the side where the pilot tests are done at SINTEF facilities in Trondheim, Norway. More information about the furnace.

3rd step

A flame emanates from the furnace, attributed to unreacted hydrogen mixing with the manganese ore. Temperatures can reach up to 900 degrees. The furnace operates for 20 hours before undergoing a 10-hour transition period for experiments. We proceed slowly to avoid thermal shock.

03

5th step

This is the furnace control room. Here, operators monitor temperatures closely to ensure smooth operations, particularly during start-up and when sampling is required.

04

4th step

The furnace is started by igniting the plasma torch in the furnace. This is done by making a shortcut between the two electrodes.

05

6th step

Temperature within the furnace is measured by multiple thermocouples embedded in the furnace shell. However, a variance typically exists between the temperature of the material and the outer shell. Consequently, every two hours, a thermocouple is introduced to precisely measure the temperature within the material. In the accompanying image, the rotation of the furnace has halted, allowing for the insertion of a thermocouple for measurement purposes.

06

